

Schmid factor aided slip pattern analysis; A method for determination of orientations of FCC crystals from slip traces

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ABSTRACT

This study introduces a novel, fast, and cost-effective method for accurate crystallographic orientation determination from slip patterns of four and three traces, and from two traces with limited certainty. The method combines established graph-based and trigonometric methods and adds three new key elements: biaxial stress, dark-field microscopy, and Schmid's law. Developed for face centered cubic (FCC) materials with low stacking fault energy and annealed structures, the method utilizes MATLAB-based algorithms and custom-built image processing software for enhanced efficiency. Its accuracy is validated against electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) data collected prior to compression testing and slip pattern analysis. The developed software tools are made available with the study. This method offers significant potential for efficient texture and slip trace analysis.

1. Introduction

Prior to the development of electron diffraction based methods, the most common way to determine crystallographic orientations in face centered cubic (FCC) metals and alloys was by manual measurement and analysis of slip plane traces or twinning boundaries revealed by light optical microscopy. Although electron diffraction based methods are becoming increasingly available in both academic and industrial research, the necessary equipment still requires significant investment and high maintenance costs compared to light optical microscopy (LOM). In addition, advances in computer controlled measurement systems in LOM have made the measurement of large areas at high magnifications a trivial task, while maintaining consistent focus and image quality. Development of a robust orientation measurement algorithm for the slip plane and annealing twin traces in LOM would bring crystallographic texture analysis within reach of a large amount of laboratories now lacking this capability. In this article, we review prior work on this topic and present a refined method utilizing a bidirectional compression test and the calculation of Schmid factors to reduce the amount of required traces for orientation determination. The method is compared against electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) measurements.

The technique of determining crystal orientation from mechanically activated slip planes, such as slip traces or twin boundaries through optical means, dates back over 80 years [1]. These features generate distinct slip patterns, each uniquely associated with a specific crystallographic orientation. Over time, significant efforts have been made to refine this technique, resulting in a variety of graphical, analytical, and numerical methods. Takeuchi et al. [2] developed charts featuring isogonic lines corresponding to measured *angles between slip traces*, where the intersection of these lines

yields the orientation's longitude and latitude, provided that all four traces are present. Drazin and Otte [3] introduced a set of methods—including graphical, analytical, and early computational approaches—for patterns with three traces, although these often produced multiple solutions (typically 4–8) via a rotation matrix. Similarly, Hoekstra et al. [4] proposed an analytical method to determine orientations in terms of *hkl* planes and *uvw* directions, yielding 2–4 solutions from three slip traces. Fong [5] combined geometrical and analytical techniques, generating multiple *hkl* solutions for patterns with three traces. More recently, Chang and Chen [6] introduced a method leveraging the angular relationships among angles between slip traces. Their approach derives a set of angles analytically, forming quadrilaterals from the traces. The correct quadrilateral—and thus the corresponding system of equations—is identified through these angular relationships. Although simpler than other analytical techniques, this method requires the presence of all four slip traces to be effective.

Collectively, prior studies represent the state of the art in determining the crystal orientation from slip traces, each contributing a distinct strategy to resolve the crystallographic orientation. This work seeks to revitalize this approach, extending its utility beyond orientation determination to rapid, cost-effective texture analysis of samples by providing tools to maximize slip plane activity, distinguish slip traces through contrasting techniques, and accurately resolve the correct orientation. In this work, half-circles are constructed from the angles between available traces. The measured angles are allocated to a predefined set within the half-circle and plotted against the corresponding orientations on an inverse pole figure (IPF), creating isogonic lines that intersect at the crystal orientation. Although previous methods have achieved similar results, they often relied on more complex procedures and did not resolve the correct solution from multiple choices [2–5]. Uniquely, this study presents three new elements to the analysis: (I) the application of biaxial stresses during compression tests to

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activate a greater number of slip planes; (II) the use of Schmid's law to eliminate erroneous solutions in cases with three traces and to refine the estimation of orientation when only two traces are present; and (III) the implementation of dark-field imaging to achieve optimal contrast in slip pattern visualization. The algorithm proposed in the study is described in detail in Chapters 2-4, and experimentally validated in Chapters 5 and 6.

2. Slip Planes and Trace Patterns in FCC Structures

Chang and Chen [6] derived the angles between slip traces in the following manner: The face-centered cubic (FCC) structure exhibits four $\{111\}$ slip planes, denoted as $P_1 = (111)$, $P_2 = (\bar{1}11)$, $P_3 = (\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$, and $P_4 = (1\bar{1}1)$. The corresponding normals to these planes are given by $\vec{P}_1 = [111]$, $\vec{P}_2 = [\bar{1}11]$, $\vec{P}_3 = [\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$, and $\vec{P}_4 = [1\bar{1}1]$. The slip line directions, \vec{L}_i , on a plane $P = (hkl)$ with unit outward normal $\vec{P} = [hkl]$, are defined in Equations 1–4. These slip lines collectively form a slip pattern on the crystal surface under deformation, as illustrated in Figure 1.

The resulting slip traces create a pattern where angles between slip traces vary depending on the crystal orientation. The sequence of these slip traces within each pattern is determined by the pole figure triangle. The specific sequence discussed here corresponds to the 001-011-111 triangle. A standard pole figure comprises 24 such triangles, each exhibiting a unique order of slip traces, yet all displaying symmetrical patterns. Consequently, angles between slip traces are equal across symmetric pairs but correspond to distinct slip planes.

Two-dimensional surface traces alone are insufficient to fully resolve the three-dimensional orientation of the crystal. Therefore, 001-011-111 triangle and a mirror counterpart, 001-101-111 triangle, are assumed. This assumption establishes a clockwise trace order as $L_1 \rightarrow L_2 \rightarrow L_4 \rightarrow L_3$ (disregarding vector direction) for the 001-011-111 triangle, or $L_1 \rightarrow L_3 \rightarrow L_4 \rightarrow L_2$ for the mirror triangle. When all four traces are present, the angles θ_{34} , θ'_{13} , θ'_{12} , and θ'_{24} sum to a half-circle. When one trace is absent, the half-circle is formed by the remaining three angles. Chang and Chen [6] ignored this, but it was something that Takeuchi et al. [2] considered. Table 1 presents all possible sets of angles forming a half-circle in a clockwise order for cases with four or three slip traces. If the angles between slip traces are found to be of anticlockwise order, the 001-101-111 mirror triangle is established.

The slip line directions are calculated as follows:

$$\vec{L}_1 = \vec{P} \times \vec{P}_1, \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{L}_2 = \vec{P} \times \vec{P}_2, \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{L}_3 = \vec{P} \times \vec{P}_3, \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{L}_4 = \vec{P} \times \vec{P}_4. \quad (4)$$

Table 1

Clockwise order of angles forming a half-circle for different missing traces in the 001–011–111 triangle.

Missing trace	Angles of half-circle
–	$\theta'_{12} \rightarrow \theta'_{24} \rightarrow \theta_{34} \rightarrow \theta'_{13}$
L_1	$\theta'_{24} \rightarrow \theta_{34} \rightarrow \theta_{23}$
L_2	$\theta_{14} \rightarrow \theta_{34} \rightarrow \theta'_{13}$
L_3	$\theta'_{12} \rightarrow \theta'_{24} \rightarrow \theta'_{14}$
L_4	$\theta'_{12} \rightarrow \theta'_{23} \rightarrow \theta'_{13}$

Table 2

Theoretical angular value ranges and trigonometric relations for angles between slip traces in the 001–011–111 triangle.

Angle	Theoretical angular value range	Trigonometric relations
θ_{12}	90°–180°	$\theta_{12} \geq \theta_{14}$ $\theta_{13} \geq \theta_{24}$ $\theta_{34} > \theta'_{12}, \theta'_{13}, \theta'_{24}$ $\theta_{23} \geq \theta'_{12}, \theta'_{13}, \theta'_{24}$
θ_{13}	120°–180°	
θ_{14}	54.74°–120°	
θ_{23}	54.74°–90°	
θ_{24}	120°–180°	
θ_{34}	60°–90°	

The angle θ_{mn} between slip lines \vec{L}_m and \vec{L}_n is determined by:

$$\theta_{mn} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\vec{L}_m \cdot \vec{L}_n}{|\vec{L}_m| |\vec{L}_n|} \right). \quad (5)$$

Table 2 presents (I) a range of theoretical angular values for each angle between slip traces and (II) trigonometric relations that are true for all orientations. Once a set of angles that satisfy conditions set by Table 1 and Table 2 is identified, the loci of the allocated angles are plotted (within a tolerance of \pm limit value) as possible orientations P on an IPF creating isogonic lines (Figure 2). For instance, consider the following example: the angle θ_{12} is assigned a measured value of 138.73°, and all orientations within the 001-011-111 triangle that match this angle are plotted in red. Similarly, θ_{13} , with measured values of 152.31°, is plotted in blue, and θ_{24} and θ_{34} , with a measured value of 140.39° and 71.43°, are plotted in magenta and cyan, respectively.

To reiterate: the loci of the measured angles are plotted as lines of possible solutions for P (orientations) on the IPF. If the set of angles is correct, these lines intersect at a single point, which corresponds to the orientation where all measured angles align with the predefined angular values. This intersection point is identified as the orientation of the observed slip pattern. However, in cases where the slip pattern consists of only three traces, multiple potential orientations may arise. To resolve this ambiguity, Schmid's law is applied, which states that the activated slip planes must exhibit the highest Schmid factors corresponding to the known stress state of the material when the slip traces have formed. This process is described in the next chapter.

Figure 1: Slip pattern guide

3. Determination of Euler Angles

The indexing process provides the orientation in terms of Miller indices, (hkl) . To calculate the Schmid factors along the loading directions (X- and Y-axis) for the determined orientation, the Euler angles ϕ_1 , Φ , and ϕ_2 must first be obtained. The second and third Euler angles, Φ and ϕ_2 , can be directly derived from normalized (hkl) indices using the relationships given in Equations 6 and 7:

$$\Phi = \cos^{-1}(l), \quad (6)$$

$$\phi_2 = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{h}{\sin(\Phi)}\right) = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{k}{\sin(\Phi)}\right). \quad (7)$$

The determination of the first Euler angle, ϕ_1 , is a slightly more tedious although straightforward process. Slip pattern analysis is conducted exclusively from the Z direction. When using the Bunge convention ('ZXZ'), this implies that the Z axis of the sample frame must serve as the point of view. Consequently, the first Euler angle, ϕ_1 , does not alter the slip pattern itself but only rotates it by the corresponding angle. Specifically, if the crystal is rotated around the Z axis by an angle ϕ_1 , the slip pattern rotates by the same amount, ϕ_1 .

To determine ϕ_1 , the relative rotational position of the pattern must be resolved. Consider *trace angle* as an angle between a slip trace and the X axis of the sample reference frame. Next, consider the pattern corresponding to the Euler angles (ϕ_1^0, Φ, ϕ_2) , where $\phi_1^0 = 0^\circ$. As all Euler angles in (ϕ_1^0, Φ, ϕ_2) are known, the corresponding trace angles of the pattern can be calculated. Thus, ϕ_1 can be determined by evaluating the angular difference between the patterns defined by (ϕ_1, Φ, ϕ_2) and (ϕ_1^0, Φ, ϕ_2) , as pictured in Figure 3.

A practical example of the whole analysis process is shown in Figures 4 and 5. An austenitic stainless steel

Figure 2: Allocated angles plotted against orientations on IPF

Figure 3: Rotation from (ϕ_1^0, Φ, ϕ_2) to (ϕ_1, Φ, ϕ_2)

(316 L) crystal with three distinct slip traces is identified and the angles between slip traces are measured from the rectangular area defined by red boundaries. Application of the algorithm for three slip traces results in two possible solutions with Euler angles $(96.73^\circ, 28.71^\circ, 34.80^\circ)$ and $(55.49^\circ, 15.48^\circ, 70.98^\circ)$. The loci of the measured angles giving the solutions are plotted on IPFs in Figures 5a and 5c. For the example specimen, the biaxial stress state resulting in the slip line traces is known and the slip activity for the potential orientations can be calculated using Schmid's law. The calculated Schmid factors for the slip planes (along with the simulated traces on the imaging plane) are shown in Figure 5b (corresponding to the solution shown in 5a) and 5d (corresponding to the solution in 5c). In case of solution of Figure 5b, $(\bar{1}11)$ plane is supposedly inactive based on the optical slip pattern. However, the calculated maximum Schmid factor for this plane is 0.45, higher than for any other plane. This contradicts the observed slip activity, indicating that Schmid's law is not satisfied, and the solution is likely incorrect. In contrast, for the solution in Figure 5d, $(\bar{1}11)$

Figure 4: Dark-field image of austenitic stainless steel crystal after biaxial compression.

plane is again presumed to be inactive with high Schmid factor, but the Schmid factors of all planes are similarly high. Therefore, the orientation $(55.49^\circ, 15.48^\circ, 70.98^\circ)$ is considered the correct solution. This is further supported by the appearance of secondary traces (representing the fourth active plane) within the smaller red-marked area, which align with the initially inactive $(\bar{1}11)$ plane.

Figure 5: Set of angles plotted against corresponding angles (a,c) and their slip patterns, respectively (b,d).

4. Analysis of Slip Patterns with Two Slip Traces

4.1. Orientation Estimation Using Two Slip Traces

In practice, slip patterns do not always exhibit three or four slip traces; often, only one or two traces are present.

A single slip trace provides insufficient information for a comprehensive analysis. However, when two slip traces are observed, a rough estimate of the orientation can be obtained by combining their analysis with Schmid's law. For instance, consider a measured angle of 137.92° . Together with its supplementary angle, this forms a half-circle. According to Table 2, this measured angle can be allocated to θ_{12} , θ_{13} , or θ_{24} . Each of these angles corresponds to a line of possible solutions, spanning a wide range of orientations on IPF.

By applying Schmid's law, which states that the activated slip traces must exhibit the highest Schmid factors, many of these potential solutions can be excluded. In this example, Schmid's law eliminates the bands associated with θ_{12} and θ_{13} , as well as a portion of the θ_{24} band. This exclusion process is illustrated in Figure 6, where the excluded and remaining solutions are represented by black and colored dots, respectively. Unlike cases with three or four slip traces, a two-trace pattern does not allow for the determination of whether the orientation corresponds to the matrix or its mirror counterpart. Consequently, both the matrix and mirror orientations must be considered when applying Schmid's law.

The matrix and mirror orientations exhibit different ϕ_2 due to switched h and k indices, thus trace angles are established for both (ϕ_1^0, Φ, ϕ_2) and $(\phi_1^0, \Phi, \phi_2)_{\text{mir}}$. Consequently, asymmetric orientations are acquired after determining ϕ_1 , except along the 001-111 line where h and k are equal. The asymmetry indicates that matrix and mirror patterns share the symmetric (hkl) orientations along the Z-axis of the sample frame but, when the crystal is rotated by 90° around the Z- or Y-axis to observe the (hkl) orientation from the Y- or X-axis perspective of the sample frame, two distinct isogonic lines appear on IPF, representing the rotated matrix and mirror orientations.

4.2. Orientation Estimation Using Single Slip Trace Twins

If the slip pattern consists of only a single slip trace but includes a twin boundary, the same analysis can be done as with two-trace patterns. In fact, the presence of a twin allows for a combined analysis, which enables orientation estimation for both the parent and twin crystals. In this case, the slip trace originating from the twin adds an additional angle to the analysis. According to geometric compatibility, the angle between slip traces in adjacent twins should also be consistent. This constraint can be used to validate potential orientation solutions.

This concept is applied in the analysis by computing the twin orientation, $(\phi_1, \Phi, \phi_2)_{\text{twin}}$, from the parent crystal, (ϕ_1, Φ, ϕ_2) . If the calculated trace angles for both the parent and twin crystals match with the optical slip traces, the orientation is considered a viable solution.

Twins introduce certain unique characteristics that can complicate the analysis. These include crystal rotation and plastic deformation in both twin and parent crystals, which can amplify the errors in the measured angles between slip traces. In addition, twin boundaries do not always produce

visible traces on the deformed surface. Often, they appear only as the junction between slip traces of adjacent twins, requiring the twin boundary to be manually drawn prior to the automatic trace detection by image processing software. When the slip traces are complete and extend to the crystal edges (as seen in Figure 4), this can be done with high precision. However, sometimes the traces are incomplete and terminate before reaching the edge of the crystal (i.e., dislocation loop has not completely opened at the surface), meaning that the twin boundary would be estimated from the remaining gap regularly observed around crystal boundaries (Figure 4). In such cases manual determination of twin boundaries is an approximation of the true boundary at best. Even minor measurement errors with traces can lead to major errors in the determination of crystal orientation, especially in [011] orientation, where 1° error in trace measurement can lead to $6 - 8^\circ$ error in orientation [2].

5. Experimental Work

Data for the experimental validation of the method was obtained by EBSD measurements followed by subsequently applied biaxial compression of the sample to obtain slip line traces, which were then identified using dark-field light optical microscopy. A 316L austenitic stainless steel plate was used as the experimental material. To achieve a large average crystal size and a recrystallized structure, the sample was annealed at 1080°C for 60 min and air-cooled to room temperature. A rectangular sample with dimensions of $13.90 \times 11.25 \times 9.60$ mm was cut, hot-mounted, and polished using a sequence of 200, 500, 800, and 1200 grit abrasives, followed by $3\ \mu\text{m}$ and $1\ \mu\text{m}$ diamond suspension polishing and $0.04\ \mu\text{m}$ colloidal silica polishing.

Electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) was performed to obtain an orientation map over a $2.0 \times 2.0\ \text{mm}^2$ area with a $4.5\ \mu\text{m}$ step size. The analysis was conducted using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (ZEISS UltraPlus) equipped with an EBSD detector (Oxford Instruments Symmetry).

The sample was removed from mounting and subjected to interrupted compression tests using an Instron 8801 100 kN testing machine. Compression was first applied in the Y-direction until a plastic strain of $\sim 1\%$ was achieved, at which point the test was interrupted. Then, the sample dimensions were remeasured to account for deformation, and compression was applied in the X-direction to the same strain level. The strain levels were deliberately kept low to minimize lattice rotation, which could complicate the analysis by deforming slip traces.

Following the compression test, the sample was analyzed using an optical microscope (Leica DMi8) in dark-field contrast mode. Images were captured from the EBSD-mapped region with high magnification to document individual crystals clearly. Slip Pattern Analysis (SPA) was performed using custom image processing software and MATLAB-based algorithms. The software automatically detected and measured trace angles, and the results were processed by

Figure 6: Plotted solutions of θ_{12} , θ_{13} and θ_{24}

Figure 7: Orientation estimation of single slip trace twins. Red line represents possible twin orientations.

the MATLAB algorithm to determine the crystallographic orientations. The evaluation between EBSD data and the orientations acquired from SPA was performed with the MTEX toolbox. All developed software tools are made available with the study.

6. Results and Discussion

6.1. Accuracy of SPA

Approximately a $2.0 \times 2.0\ \text{mm}^2$ area was mapped using EBSD. Figure 8a shows a cropped section of the map. The same area was imaged with an optical microscope in dark-field contrast (Figure 8b), with the X and Y axes aligned to match the orientation map. SPA was performed on 99 crystals, each showing slip pattern of three or four traces (slip traces + twin boundaries). The results obtained were assigned to the corresponding crystals of the EBSD orientation map, as presented in Figure 8c. Crystals that were not analyzed are presented in gray. The misorientation between the EBSD and SPA-derived orientations for each analyzed crystal is presented in a separate misorientation map (Figure 8d). There were some instances where multiple solutions fulfilled Schmid's law, but for the sake of clarity, only solutions matching the EBSD results were included. The IPF key used for orientation coloring refers to the Z direction in the sample reference plane. It is provided in Figure 9.

It is evident from the maps that there are significant misorientations between the EBSD and SPA-derived orientations. The distribution of the misorientations is presented in Figure 10. The median misorientation is approximately 6° , which is unexpectedly high. This discrepancy can be further illustrated by examining the deviations in the trace angles. Figure 11 presents the differences between optically measured trace angles and the corresponding angles calculated from the EBSD results. The median deviation is

Figure 8: (a) EBSD orientation map, (b) optical micrograph of the analyzed area in dark-field contrast, (c) orientations determined by Slip Pattern Analysis and (d) misorientations between EBSD and Slip Pattern Analysis.

Figure 9: IPF color key.

approximately 3°. Such deviations between EBSD-derived

and experimentally observed trace angles are not uncommon; several studies have presented results with clear trace deviations even at low strain levels (<4 %) [7–11].

It is well-known that EBSD suffers from accuracy limitations due to several sources of error, including sample positioning in the scanning electron microscope chamber, as well as the acquisition and indexing of the diffraction patterns. According to the equipment manufacturer [12], these factors can collectively contribute to orientation errors exceeding 2°, which is reflected in elevated Mean Angular Deviation (MAD) values. MAD represents the comparison of the measured angles of the diffraction bands in an EBSD pattern and the corresponding angles predicted by the simulated pattern based on the determined crystal orientation. For the SPA method, it is possible to perform a conceptually similar evaluation by comparing the measured traces and

Figure 10: Misorientations between EBSD and SPA.

the simulated traces based on the determined orientation. Figure 12 shows the EBSD and SPA MAD distributions in the same graph. Majority of the slip plane traces exhibited extremely good fits with the determined orientations, which indicates that lattice rotation during compression testing was minimal and did not significantly alter the observed slip patterns. Regarding the MAD differences, it is important to note that MAD in SPA is determined from three or four traces, whereas in EBSD the value is determined from a much larger number of Kikuchi bands. This means that EBSD has far more constraints in trying to fit the measured pattern to the indexed one, which may partially explain the huge gap in MAD distributions observed in Figure 12.

The application of Schmid's law is a critical part of SPA. Figure 13 presents the relationship of Schmid factors with slip activity and the fulfillment of Schmid's law in three-trace patterns. Both graphs were obtained from the SPA results. Approximately two-thirds of the patterns were consistent with Schmid's law, i.e., the inactive planes have lower Schmid factors than the active planes. These findings should be interpreted with caution due to the influence of subsequently applied biaxial stress conditions.

6.2. Potential Slip Pattern Characteristics and Slip Behavior Applicable in SPA

The analysis carried out in this study was based on the methods presented in Chapters 2 and 3 and is therefore applicable only to crystals that exhibit slip patterns with three or four traces. The results revealed an inconsistent correlation between slip plane activation and Schmid's law. Because the analysis of two-trace patterns heavily relies on an accurate application of Schmid's law, such cases were excluded from this study. Convincing analysis of two-trace patterns requires knowledge of the local stress direction, which arises from interactions between adjacent crystals and their active slip systems. Specifically, activated slip directions in neighboring crystals induce local stress fields, which can be seen as concentration of a specific slip trace within the crystal. Resolving the local stress direction is one

Figure 11: Trace angle deviation between indexed patterns from EBSD data and optically measured slip patterns.

Figure 12: Mean angular deviations of EBSD and SPA results.

way to improve SPA for cases with two traces. Note that sub-surface crystals interact with surface crystals, too, creating uncertainty in the analysis. Other techniques or phenomena that can enhance SPA include, but are not limited to: analysis of Burgers vector components, slip transfer across crystal boundaries, trace frequency analysis, and the relationship between orientation and the number of activated slip planes.

In certain cases, a slip system may exhibit a high Schmid factor yet fail to produce a visible slip trace due to a near-zero z-component in the Burgers vector [9]. This behavior could be advantageous for SPA, as the z-component of the Burgers vector may correlate with the brightness or intensity of the slip trace. Similarly, the x- and y-components may influence the apparent thickness of the trace. These variations in trace appearance could potentially be exploited to identify the active slip systems more precisely and, consequently, to narrow down the possible solutions.

Plastic slip and slip transfer are not isolated events. Instead, they are competing mechanisms for deformation accommodation, so that an increase in the probability of one

Figure 13: (a) Schmid factors of active and inactive planes of SPA-derived orientations. (b) Fulfillment of Schmid's Law in patterns of three traces.

corresponds to a decrease in the probability of the other [9]. For example, when multiple slip systems are available within a crystal, the need for slip transfer across crystal boundaries decreases. In contrast, when fewer slip systems are available, slip transfer becomes more probable. As a result, slip transfer is expected to occur more frequently in two-trace patterns than with three- or four-trace patterns. In principle, the Luster–Morris parameter [13], which quantifies the likelihood of slip transfer between pairs of slip systems across crystal boundaries, could be applied to filter out solutions that do not meet the conditions set by the parameter. The formula for the parameter is the following: $m' = \cos \kappa \cos \psi$, where κ is the angle between slip directions and ψ is the angle between plane normals.

Schmid's law not only predicts the slip planes most likely to activate but also enables predictions regarding the frequency or spacing of the slip traces. Figure 14 presents a series of schematic slip patterns involving slip traces L_m and L_n . In all cases, the trace angles of L_m and L_n , as well as the measured angle θ_{mn} , remain consistent. However, each pattern is unique and can be readily distinguished from the others, reflecting the expected slip behavior under varying Schmid factor differences. When the Schmid factor of one slip system, SF_m , is significantly larger than that of another, SF_n , the L_m traces appear more frequently. As the difference between the Schmid factors decreases, the difference in trace frequency diminishes accordingly. When the Schmid factors are equal, the trace frequencies of L_m and L_n become equivalent. Additionally, Figure 14 includes zigzag patterns that illustrate cross-slip, a phenomenon that occurs between slip planes sharing a mutual slip direction. The zigzag trace tends to skew toward the slip trace with the higher Schmid factor. In cases where the Schmid factors are equal, the zigzag trace is expected to persist at a neutral angle with respect to the angles of the observed slip traces, as shown in the bottom-center hex of Figure 14.

Figure 14: Slip pattern types of two slip traces.

Different crystallographic orientations exhibit varying Schmid factors, and as a result, the number of traces in a slip pattern is inherently linked to the crystal orientation. The [001] orientations have high Schmid factors for all four planes in either the X or Y loading direction. Consequently, slip patterns in [001]-oriented crystals are likely to have three or four traces. In contrast, [011] and [111] orientations have a slip direction and a slip plane, respectively, in the 90° angle range with respect to the loading directions. This geometry leads to near-zero Schmid factors for two or three slip systems, resulting in fewer systems available for activation. Following this logic, these orientations are statistically less likely to produce slip patterns with three or four traces. As a result, SPA is inherently biased toward [001] orientations.

6.3. Applications of Slip Pattern Analysis

The possible applications of SPA are determined by its characteristics: speed and cost-efficiency, high accuracy and precision, requirement of straight slip traces and multiple plane activation, as well as requirement of uniform crystal size and shape. The requirement of straight slip traces immediately limits the possible applications to materials with low stacking-fault energy, such as austenitic stainless steels or copper alloys. The processing of these materials must be such that the microstructure has minimal sub-crystal misorientation and is uniform in crystal size and shape. Dislocations induce waviness in slip traces which, in turn, increases MAD of indexed orientations. Obscure crystal shapes may complicate the distinguishing of one crystal from another, and a broad crystal size distribution may leave the smallest crystals unaffected. SPA could be used to analyze the texture of sheet and plate products, provided that the conditions mentioned above are met.

Additive manufacturing (AM), particularly laser powder bed fusion, has a high interest in texture analysis and can easily integrate SPA to its production process. Standard cube samples are routinely prepared and examined using optical microscopy, requiring only the addition of a hydraulic press to integrate SPA into the workflow. Unfortunately, as-manufactured AM sample has all the undesirable

microstructure characteristics mentioned earlier. Thus, SPA could only be used after a suitable heat treatment.

Ideas for improving the reliability of SPA on two-trace patterns were discussed in Chapter 6.2. If these approaches prove to be effective, they could significantly expand the applicability of SPA in texture analysis. In materials containing annealing twins, even a single mechanically induced slip trace may suffice for orientation estimation. Moreover, if an accurate orientation estimation can be achieved from two-trace patterns, the use of biaxial stress would no longer be necessary. Instead, uniaxial loading would be sufficient or even preferable. Analyzing crystal interactions becomes considerably more straightforward when only one stress direction is applied. However, SPA of two-trace patterns under uniaxial stress faces a similar limitation as SPA of three- or four-trace patterns under biaxial stress: an insufficient number of activated slip planes to account for all crystals. Under biaxial stress, many crystals exhibit only two traces, while under uniaxial stress, many show only one. In both cases, the use of materials with annealing twins can greatly increase the number of crystals for which orientation can be reliably determined. Therefore, SPA would be most effective with materials that have annealing twins.

7. Conclusions

This study presents a novel method for determining the orientation of FCC crystals that is both fast and cost-effective. SPA was demonstrated to work with three- and four-trace patterns with reasonable accuracy. An argument was given for orientation estimation from two-trace patterns.

The use of SPA on a crystal with a slip pattern of only two traces is not feasible because the local stress direction may differ from the global stress direction, which limits the applicability of Schmid's law. To determine orientations in such cases, it is necessary to adopt a broader perspective that considers the crystal and its neighboring crystals in terms of geometric compatibility. Instead of analyzing crystals individually (an approach that works with three- and four-trace patterns), they should be considered as a collective, where the slip behavior of one crystal constrains the slip behavior of the others.

The fundamental reasoning behind the analysis of slip patterns is that a slip pattern generated by plastic deformation is not random but a systematic representation of plastic events related to that crystal, like a fingerprint. The information is stored as trace angles, frequency, brightness, and concentration of slip traces. The question is to what extent these two-dimensional surface traits can be leveraged in solving three-dimensional crystallographic orientations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jani Penttilä: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing - original draft. **Tuomo Nyysönen:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **Veli-Tapani Kuokkala:** Writing - review & editing.

Lassi Raami: Methodology. **Pasi Peura:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the first author used Grok 3 (xAI) and ChatGPT (OpenAI) in order to improve the readability and flow of the text. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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